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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF ESOMEPRAZOLE CONTROLLED RELEASE TABLETS BY USING VARIOUS GRADES OF EUDRAGIT POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the contemporary research work was to develop the controlled release tablets of esomeprazole. Esomeprazole having a shorter biological half life (1-1.5 hours) hence we are selected as a controlled release tablet, So it should be minimize the dose dumping problems and avoid fluctuations in plasma drug concentrations. To maintain constant therapeutic levels of the drug over 24 hours. Compatibility studies was execution during FTIR and DSC shown that there was absence of probable chemical interaction between pure drug and excipients. Controlled release tablets were prepared by direct compression method using altered concentrations of Eudragit-S 100, Eudragit-L 100 and Eudragit-RSPO. Esomeprazole dose was fixed as 20 mg. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 100 mg. Polymers were used in the concentration of 20 and 40 mg. Prepared compositions were evaluating the various physicochemical parameters such as weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness and drug content. All the compositions were resulted in adequate Pharmacopoeial limits. Whereas from the dissolution studies it was evident that the formulation (F-6) showed better desired drug release pattern i.e., 97.47% in 24 hours. It followed Zero Order release kinetics mechanism. As the consequence of this amendment it could conclude that the compositions rally the needed theoretical drug release profile as well as has the controlled action i.e., retarded the drug release, Hence so the release is for a long time and thus more Bioavailability. The optimised formula shall be utilized for the formulation development and other studies like bioequivalence study, for triumphant initiation of the product.

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INTRODUCTION

Esomeprazole is a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) which blocks the production of acid by the stomach. It is used in the treatment of Peptic ulcer disease, Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and Zollinger-Ellison Syndrome.

The goal in designing a controlled delivery system is to reduce the frequency of dosing or to increase the effectiveness of the drug by localization at the site of action, reducing the dose required or providing uniform drug delivery.

The primary objectives of controlled drug delivery are to ensure safety and to improve efficacy of drugs as well as patient compliance. This is achieved by better control of plasma drug levels and less frequent dosing.^[1, 2]

To formulate and evaluate Esomeprazole controlled release tablets using different polymers such as Eudragit grades, Talc, Magnesium Stearate and Di Calcium Phosphate.

The Main Objective of this study was to improve the bioavailability, reduce the number of doses and to increase patient compliance it was formulated as controlled release tablets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Esomeprazole was a procured from Micro Labs, Bangalore, Eudragit grades was supplied by Yarrow Chem. Products, Mumbai, and Talc, Magnesium Stearate, Di calcium phosphate were supplied by Signet Chemical Corporation, Mumbai, India.

METHODOLOGY

Analytical method development:

Determination of absorption maxima:

A solution of containing the concentration 10 µg/ml was prepared in 0.1N HCl, 6.8 P^H & phosphate buffer 7.4 P^H respectively, UV spectrum was taken using Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer. The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400nm.

Preparation calibration curve:

10mg of drug was accurately weighed and dissolved in 10ml of 0.1N HCl, 6.8 P^H, and 7.4 P^H in 10 ml volumetric flask, to make (1000 µg/ml) standard stock solution (1). Then 1 ml stock solution (1) was taken in another 10 ml volumetric flask to make (100 µg/ml) standard stock solution (2), then again 1 ml of stock solution (2) was taken in another 10 ml volumetric flask and then final concentrations were prepared 2, 4, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40 µg/ml with 0.1N HCl, 6.8 P^H, and 7.4 P^H. The absorbance of standard solution was determined using UV/ VIS spectrophotometer at 273nm. Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (r²) which determined by least-square linear regression analysis.

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies:

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The physical properties of the physical assortment were comparing with those of esomeprazole pure drug. Samples was assorted comprehensively through 100mg potassium bromide IR powder as well as compacted under vacuum at a pressure of concerning 12 psi for 3 minutes. The ensuing disc was mounted in an appropriate holder in Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer and the IR spectrum was recorded from 3500 cm to 500 cm. The resultant spectrum was compared for any spectrum changes.^[3,4]

Preformulation parameters:

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per Pharmacopoeia.^[5-7]

Formulation development of Tablets:

Preparation of tablets:

Direct compression method: Different tablets formulations were prepared by direct compression technique. All powders were passed through 60 mesh. Required quantities of drug and polymers were mixed thoroughly Magnesium stearate was added as lubricant. Talc was used as glidant. Micro crystalline cellulose was used as diluent. Finally the powder mix was subjected to compression after mixing uniformly in a polybag. Prior to compression, the blends were evaluated for several tests.^[8,9]

Table 1: Formulation composition for Esomeprazole tablets.

INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Esomeprazole	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Eudragit S-100	20	40	-	-	-	-	20	20	-
Eudragit L-100	-	-	20	40	-	-	20	-	20
Eudragit RSPO	-	-	-	-	20	40	-	-	20
Talc	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	3
Di.Calcium Phosphate	Qs								
Total Weight	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

All are expressed in mg.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Evaluation of Esomeprazole controlled release tablets:

Analytical Method:

Graphs of Esomeprazole were taken in Simulated Gastric fluid (pH 1.2) and in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 238 nm and 236 nm respectively.

Table 2: Observations for graph of Esomeprazole in 0.1N HCl (238nm).

Conc.[$\mu\text{g/l}$]	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.110
10	0.214
15	0.304
20	0.407
25	0.510
30	0.621
35	0.718
40	0.815

Figure 1: Standard graph of Esomeprazole in 0.1N HCl.**Table 3: Observations for graph of Esomeprazole in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer (236nm).**

Conc.[$\mu\text{g/l}$]	Absorbance
5	0.098
10	0.195
15	0.298
20	0.392
25	0.490
30	0.595
35	0.690
40	0.776

Figure 2: Standard graph of Esomeprazole pH 6.8 phosphate buffer (236nm).

Table 4: Preformulation parameters of powder blend:

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	24.13	0.51±0.02	0.53±0.03	15.96±0.08	0.98±0.05
F2	23.36	0.50±0.03	0.54±0.06	16.18±0.04	1.03±0.06
F3	24.69	0.49±0.09	0.57±0.04	14.68±0.07	1.08±0.09
F4	25.26	0.52±0.07	0.53±0.06	16.59±0.09	1.01±0.03
F5	24.98	0.53±0.07	0.58±0.05	15.84±0.06	1.1±0.07
F6	24.12	0.54±0.02	0.55±0.08	14.98±0.02	1.10±0.08
F7	23.86	0.55±0.08	0.58±0.03	15.98±0.04	0.94±0.06
F8	25.02	0.56±0.02	0.63±0.04	14.84±0.03	1.14±0.08
F9	24.98	0.54±0.03	0.53±0.04	16.98±0.08	1.09±0.03

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.49±0.09 to 0.56±0.02 (gm/cm³) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.53±0.03 to 0.58±0.05 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be ranging between 14.68±0.07 to 16.98±0.08 which shows that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations has shown the hausner's ratio ranging between 0.94±0.06 to 1.14±0.08 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Quality Control Parameters for Esomeprazole tablets:

Esomeprazole Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, Drug content and drug release studies in different media were performed on the compression tablet.^[10-12]

Table 5: In vitro quality control parameters for Esomeprazole tablets.

Time (hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	6.98	6.42	7.08	7.35	15.55	6.42	14.21	10.53	10.11
2	7.86	8.52	18.73	14.39	19.94	12.59	19.65	19.29	16.74
4	14.65	13.26	27.74	19.22	28.33	24.26	24.98	29.21	28.37
6	18.64	22.73	39.11	24.21	35.29	38.12	28.76	36.36	33.44
8	23.36	33.79	47.44	31.42	40.11	49.94	35.34	41.39	43.45
10	29.82	41.21	58.35	39.73	48.87	57.15	44.50	49.62	49.34
12	34.61	50.22	63.53	51.29	55.83	69.93	54.56	58.01	58.11
14	43.07	57.33	69.89	60.11	61.12	75.66	61.05	65.47	66.94
16	48.71	68.03	74.29	72.14	69.76	81.78	64.98	73.55	69.38
18	57.22	74.39	79.01	78.77	73.58	85.19	72.03	77.48	74.14
20	68.35	76.15	81.43	83.64	79.56	91.26	76.92	80.35	79.76
22	77.23	81.12	83.36	86.89	85.32	94.18	85.88	84.66	84.88
24	86.77	88.27	90.67	91.03	91.93	97.47	91.12	90.87	89.98

All the parameters such as weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness and drug content were found to be within limits.

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies:

Table 6: Cumulative percent drug release of Esomeprazole Tablets:

Formulation codes	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
F1	100±0.48	4.5±0.41	0.50±0.13	3.8±0.29	99.17±0.73
F2	101.4±0.86	4.1±0.23	0.59±0.48	4.1±0.24	98.96±0.36
F3	99.1±0.86	3.9±0.16	0.61±0.29	3.4±0.14	99.74±0.64
F4	101.6±0.86	3.5±0.39	0.75±0.66	4.9±0.57	98.96±0.11
F5	98.9±0.11	4.2±0.22	0.56±0.25	3.9±0.35	99.59±0.35
F6	99.8±0.32	4.4±0.56	0.65±0.18	4.1±0.23	99.87±0.13
F7	98.4±0.53	3.8±0.12	0.59±0.74	3.4±0.24	98.85±0.37
F8	101.3±0.42	3.3±0.11	0.49±0.33	3.3±0.61	99.36±0.31
F9	99.1±0.44	3.8±0.37	0.57±0.37	3.5±0.27	99.61±0.44

Figure 3: Dissolution graphs for the formulations F1-F3.

Figure 4: Dissolution graphs for the formulations F4-F6.

Figure 5: Dissolution graphs for the formulations F7-F9.

From the dissolution data it was evident that the formulations prepared with Eudragit-RSPO as polymer were suitable to retard the drug release up to desired time period i.e., 24 hours.

Whereas the formulations prepared with Eudragit RSPO retarded the drug release in the concentration of 20 mg (F-6 Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release upto 24 hours and showed maximum of 97.47% in 24 hours with good retardation.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero order, first order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer-Peppas and Hixson Crowell release model.^[13-15]

Table 7: Different kinetic models for tablets:

F.Code	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	Hixson Crowell
F1	0.9898	0.9810	0.9337	0.9656	0.9856
F2	0.9939	0.9787	0.9072	0.9660	0.9863
F3	0.9769	0.9971	0.9728	0.9781	0.9959
F4	0.9853	0.9580	0.9196	0.9748	0.9711
F5	0.9604	0.9869	0.9878	0.9864	0.9827
F6	0.9929	0.9848	0.9461	0.9979	0.9951
F7	0.9667	0.9653	0.9531	0.9517	0.9706
F8	0.9727	0.9877	0.9814	0.9928	0.9886
F9	0.9829	0.9869	0.9728	0.9967	0.9917

Optimized Formulation for Release Kinetics Graphs:

Figure 6(a): Zero order release.

Figure 6(b): First order release.

Figure 6(c): Higuchi.

Figure 6(d): Karsmayer peppas.

Figure 6(e): Hixson Crowell.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the present study was to develop a controlled release formulation of proton pump inhibitor (PPI) of Esomeprazole. To maintain constant therapeutic levels of the drug for over 24 hrs. Esomeprazole was selected as model drugs. Various formulations were developed with different polymers for each drug molecule. To achieve pH-independent drug release of formulations, pH modifying agents (buffering agents) were used. The precompression blend of all formulations was subjected to various flow property tests and all the formulations were passed the tests.

Esomeprazole:

Esomeprazole dose was fixed as 20 mg. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 100 mg. Polymers were used in the concentration of 20 and 40 mg concentration. All the formulations were passed various physicochemical evaluation parameters and they were found to be within limits. Whereas from the dissolution studies it was evident that the formulation (F-6) showed better and desired drug release pattern i.e., 97.47 % in 24 hours. It followed zero order release kinetics mechanism. The best formulation was repeated again for reproducibility, and all the quality control tests were done for conformation. The results were found to be super imposable with each other. The optimized formula shall be utilized for the formulation development and other studies like bio-equivalence study, for successful launching of the product.

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Abbreviations

1. CR: Controlled Release
2. PPI: Proton Pump Inhibitor
3. GERD: Gastroesophageal reflux disease
4. FTIR: Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy
5. DSC: Differential Scanning Calorimetry

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